

Review Article

The Influence of Exchange Rate, Trade Openness, Inflation, and Gross Domestic Product on Stock Market Performance in Tanzania

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Abstract

The research focused on the connection between the exchange rate, trade openness, inflation, the gross domestic product (GDP) growth rate, and stock market performance, specifically market capitalisation, in Tanzania at Dar es Salaam Stock Exchange (DSE). The secondary quarterly time series data from 2006Q1 to 2023Q4 were analysed in this study, sourced from the Bank of Tanzania, the National Bureau of Statistics, and the Dar es Salaam Stock Exchange. Using a quantitative approach, the study applied the ARDL Model to analyse the data after testing for cointegration with the ARDL Bounds Test. The Error Correction Model accounted for short-run dynamics, with Granger Causality serving as a robustness test. The study found a significant and positive relationship between exchange rate, GDP growth rate, and trade openness and stock market capitalisation in the long-run, with inflation having no significant effect. The results further show that exchange rate changes remain significantly positive in the short-run regardless of the insignificant effects of trade openness and GDP. Moreover, the results signal a minimal, significant negative effect for inflation. The results underscore strengthening fiscal and monetary policies and

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regulations to boost investor's confidence and improve listings to further boost Tanzania's stock market capitalisation. Enhanced market performance can expedite the execution of Tanzania's 2050 development vision which pinpoints the stock market as a source of financing for development projects.

Keywords: Dar es Salaam stock exchange, exchange rate, GDP growth rate, inflation, stock market performance, trade openness.

Introduction

The stock market brings together potential investors and listed firms to provide investment opportunities (Moussa and Delhoumi, 2022). It facilitates mobilising savings, allocating and accessing capital, as well as enhancing liquidity (Akileng et al., 2018). Its contribution to the country's economic growth is considerable. In China, for example, the gross domestic product grew to \$11 trillion by 2016, and market capitalisation exceeded \$7 trillion by 2017, thus making it the second-largest global economy (Carpenter & Whitelaw, 2017).

African countries have also benefited significantly from stock markets. The number of stock markets rose from five (5) in Sub-Saharan Africa (SSA) and three (3) in North Africa prior to 1989 to more than 29 stock markets currently, according to Thaddeus et al. (2024). In line with developments elsewhere, Tanzania introduced the Dar es Salaam Stock Exchange (DSE) in 1996 under the Capital Markets and Securities Authority (CMSA) Act. In April 1998, the DSE became fully operational. Currently, the DSE lists 28 companies, comprising 22 local firms and 6 cross-listed entities (DSE, 2022).

Thus far, the stock market in Tanzania has shown significant improvements in its operations (DSE, 2022; Kapaya, 2020), including the establishment of an enterprise growth market forum and an online trading system that allows trading on mobile phones (DSE, 2019, 2023). Nonetheless, DSE performance remains underperforming, as shown by inconsistent performance in market capitalisation, the market index, and trading volume (see Figure 1). Inconsistencies in stock market performance signal unsatisfactory performance, as noted by Rakhil (2018). Therefore, this raises a concern about the performance of the DSE, providing a basis for this research, which evaluates the effects of exchange rates, trade openness, inflation, and GDP growth rate on Tanzania's stock market performance.

Factors such as GDP growth, inflation, exchange rates, and trade openness contribute to the stock market performance (El-Masry & Badr, 2021; Javangwe & Takawira, 2022; Kaustia et al., 2023; Onafowora & Owoye, 2024). The exchange rate is a key variable in an open economy, as it facilitates international trade (Javangwe & Takawira, 2022). Moreover, the exchange rate promotes the growth and investment of listed companies. Furthermore, movements in exchange rates can enhance the effectiveness and efficiency of fiscal policy, which in turn impacts stock market performance (Aftab et al., 2024). Similarly, as advocated by Keswani et al. (2024) and Şen et al. (2020), as well as Kasongwa and Minja (2022), inflation rate and GDP substantially contribute to stock market performance as important drivers of the economy based on their influence on

determining the economic performance, pricing, investment decisions, and financial conditions of the listed entities and the stock market.

Figure 1: Stock Market Performance at DSE. Source: DSE Annual Reports (2011-2022)

Moreover, trade significantly drives the prosperity and global economic growth (Onafowora & Owoye, 2024). Usually, trade involves both exports and imports in an environment of economic openness (Nam & Ryu, 2024). Such a trade environment also influences the output of listed firms and the stock market generally, thereby contributing to sustainable economic growth and prosperity, much in line with the systems theory, which views the stock market as one component of the financial system, which is a component of the economic system (Allen & Gale, 2000). This supports the view that the economy is an interconnected set of components in which parts affect one another (Bertalanffy, 1969; Yang et al., 2023). In other words, the stock market interacts with other components of the financial and economic system, such as trade openness, exchange rates, GDP, and inflation, which in turn affect the stock market (Javanmardi et al., 2023).

Although exchange rate, trade openness, inflation, and GDP play a key role in boosting stock market performance, studies on these factors are largely limited in many developing countries, including Tanzania. In addition, available studies have overlooked the economic growth-trade openness (Nam & Ryu, 2024; Nwadike Johnmary & Alamba, 2020; Kumari et al., 2023; Onafowora & Owoye, 2024). In addition, some previous scholar have highted on tax revenue, financial depth, environmental sustainability, and financial development (Akhayere et al., 2023; Ho et al., 2023). Nonetheless, these studies occurred mostly in developed countries, whose operational environments differ significantly from those in developing countries, particularly in Tanzania, as indicated by Aftab et al. (2024) and El-Diftar (2023). El-Masry and Badr (2021), and Javangwe and Takawira (2022).

The inability to generalise these findings stems from heterogeneous factors such as culture, regulatory frameworks, and economic dynamics. Inevitably, this limits the

application of their results to the Tanzanian context. Thus, this study assesses the influence of exchange rates, inflation, trade openness, and GDP growth rate on Tanzania's stock market performance to fill this knowledge gap. Specifically, the study set out to examine the effect of the exchange rate on stock market performance; assess the impact of Trade openness on stock market performance; examine the influence of the relationship between Inflation rates and stock market performance; and examine the relationship between GDP growth rate and stock market performance.

This study contributes by extending the application of existing theory (systems theory) by integrating exchange rates, trade openness, inflation, GDP growth rate, and stock market performance into the country's financial system. Moreover, it underscores how policymakers in developing countries must strengthen regulations and monetary and fiscal policies to improve the stock market's intended performance. Generally, exploring the link among these variables provides market participants and investors with insights essential in making informed investment decisions and forecast market trends. In addition to this introduction, the second section reviews studies on exchange rates, trade openness, stock market performance, and connectivity. The subsequent section deals with the study's methodology. The fourth section presents and analyses the research findings, coupled with a discussion of our findings, and the last section presents the conclusion, along with policy recommendations and suggests areas for future research.

Literature Review and Hypotheses Development

Theoretical review

Systems theory suggests that various components, operating within open or closed systems, explain the performance of an entity, including stock markets (Becvar & Reif, 2023; Chick, 2023). In a closed system, link between numerous components of a company affect its performance. Such a closed system includes internal factors that describe an entity's performance. Since no entity operates in a completely closed system, as noted by Javanmardi et al. (2023), this underscores the importance of assessing firms' performance by considering external factors, such as macroeconomic attributes, which are found in an open system. Thus, from a systems theory perspective, GDP, inflation, exchange rates, and trade openness, as macroeconomic parameters, engage with stock markets as components of the financial and economic system (De Haan et al., 2020). As such, this study applies systems theory to examine the effects of GDP growth rate, inflation, trade openness, and exchange rates on Tanzania's stock market performance.

Empirical Review

Exchange Rate and Stock Market Performance

The exchange rates-stock market performance relationship attracts various scholars in developed and some emerging economies alike, particularly among practitioners and academia. Implicitly, most of these studies have limited applicability to developing countries such as Tanzania, thus necessitating the present study. For example, a study across emerging and developed countries highlighted that innovations in exchange rates have negative short-term but positive long-term impacts on stock market prices, as noted

by Javangwe and Takawira (2022) in their application of the ARDL method in South Africa. In other words, when policymakers make fiscal and monetary policy decisions, their actions affect the exchange rate-stock market relationship. This observation aligns with El-Masry and Badr (2021), who reported that in Egypt, confirmed stock market indices-foreign exchange market correlation during revolutionary sessions by running a vector autoregression model. Moreover, market capitalisation-operationalised stock market performance had a positive link with the exchange rate when applying fixed, random, and pooled models, as noted by Alshubiri (2021).

Also, Ghumro et al. (2024) found that the exchange rate effects on stock market performance are less substantial than those of investor sentiment in both the long-run and short-term. In contrast, El-Diftar's (2023) results from a related examination indicate that a significant positive long-term linkage exists between stock market returns and exchange rates in all seven (7) emerging economies, but not in Indonesia. Furthermore, Keswani et al. (2024) documented a negative correlation between the Indian stock market and monthly exchange rate observations. Thus, the current study's knowledge gap emanates from these mixed results, which suggest inconclusive evidence. Collectively, these arguments allow this study to hypothesise:

H₁: The exchange rate positively influences stock market performance.

Trade Openness and Stock Market Performance

Although trade openness is indubitably a key player in socioeconomic development in an increasingly globalised world (Nam & Ryu, 2024; Nam et al., 2025), considerable debate rages among economic development practitioners and academia on trade openness and the stock market (Wang et al., 2025). Moreover, previous scholars have shown a positive and significant trade openness-economic growth connectivity employing ordinary least squares (OLS) and ARDL in Nigeria and Afghanistan, as noted by Nwadike, Johnmary, and Alamba (2020) and Wani (2019), respectively. Furthermore, Ho and Odhiambo (2018), Nwadike et al. (2020), and Olokoyo et al. (2020) highlight the value of trade openness in enhancing stock market activities in Nigeria, using OLS and VECM models, respectively. Consequently, trade openness is invaluable for assessing its influence on developing countries' stock market performance, particularly in Tanzania. Similarly, Bitu et al. (2025) noted that although trade openness is important for ensuring a conducive business environment, it has received little attention in developing countries. Thus, we examine the trade openness and stock market performance relationship in Tanzania to test the following hypothesis:

H₂: Trade openness positively affects stock market performance.

Inflation and Stock Market Performance

Although stocks can hedge against inflation effects according to theory, prior studies have reported mixed and inconsistent results on the inflation-stock performance linkage. Choi et al.'s (2020) study, conducted in the United States' developed financial market, found that higher inflation reduces stock market activity returns due to its adverse effect on economic growth and corporate profitability. Likewise, Batabyal and Killins (2021)

discovered a negative association between inflation and stock market returns in Canada. Meanwhile, Gudimella et al. (2025) reported similar findings, suggesting that inflation can destabilise the market and erode investor confidence.

Conversely, Gharios et al.'s (2024) study on the financial performance of listed non-financial European businesses found that moderate inflation promotes stock returns by increasing economic spending and expanding economic activity. Moreover, Bahadur and Adhikari (2025) applied time-series data, cointegration and vector autoregression models. They found mixed results on the association between inflation and stock market performance in Nepal. Implicitly, the connection between inflation and stock market performance remains uncertain, underscoring the need for further country-specific analyses. Nonetheless, in Tanzania, on a limited scale, Kasongwa and Minja (2022) established a significant but negative inflation and stock market performance. Nevertheless, their findings, though relevant, focused on oil prices and stock market performance measured by the all-share market index; this study includes a broader range of macroeconomic parameters and stock market capitalisation to comprehensively determine stock market performance at the DSE. Based on these arguments, we hypothesise:

H₃: There is a negative inflation rate-stock market performance relationship.

Gross Domestic Product (GDP) and Stock Market Performance

Scholars such as Olokoyo et al. (2020), who assessed the GDP-stock market performance linkage, reported mixed results, suggesting that, although GDP shapes stock market movements, reported a positive GDP growth-stock market performance connection, yet weak in the long-run in Nigeria. As for Keswani et al. (2024), who analysed monthly observations in India, found a positive and significant relationship between GDP and stock market returns. On the other hand, Patatoukas's (2021) study in the US found no significant relationship between GDP news and stock market returns in the Philadelphia market, although theories presume the simultaneous growth of stock market performance and economic growth. In similar vein, Ali (2023), who applied a vector error correction model, found no correlation between GDP and movements in the Dhaka stock market. Collectively, inconsistencies, confirming the existence of heterogeneity factors and thus cannot be applied in the Tanzanian context. Accordingly, this study adopted the following hypothesis:

H₄: GDP growth rate and stock market performance are positively and significantly connected.

Methodology

The study used 2006q1 - 2023q4 the Bank of Tanzania (BoT), the National Bureau of Statistics (NBS), and the Dar es Salaam Stock Exchange (DSE) secondary time series data. As Kalam (2020) reported, data availability determined the selection of coverage years. The quantitative approach enabled the study to examine the effects of the exchange rate, trade openness, inflation, and the gross domestic product (GDP) growth rate on the DSE stock market performance. Stock market capitalisation a dependent variable

facilitated the measurement and prediction of stock market performance, given its key role in representing the value of market-traded stocks and, by extension, reflecting overall market performance (Ho, 2019). As Table 1 further illustrates, the study employs exchange rates, inflation, GDP growth rate, and trade openness as independent parameters to explain the dependent stock market performance factor:

Table 1. Variable Operationalisation

S/N	Variables	Conceptual Definition	Measurements	Sources
1	Independent	Exchange rate	Official exchange rate during a year (TZS), converted to the average quarterly	(Ashour, Sayed, & Abbas, 2023)
		Trade openness	The sum of imported and exported products and services expressed as a percentage of GDP (US\$ billions), used on an average quarterly basis	(WB, 2020; Fagbemi, Adeosun, & Bello, 2021)
		GDP	Real GDP change per annum (%-growth rate), applied to the quarterly growth rate	(Ashour, Sayed, & Abbas, 2023)
		Inflation	Consumer Price Index (CPI)'s annual change, analysed quarterly	(Ashour, Sayed, & Abbas, 2023)
2	Dependent	Stock market performance	Market Capitalisation = Sum of shares outstanding multiplied by the closing price for each share (TZ billions)	(Kumar & Kumara, 2021).

Model Specification

To estimate and model the links among exchange rates, trade openness, GDP, and stock market performance, this study proposes the following general model:

$$MC = f(ER, TO, IR, GDP) \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

Where; $MC = \ln\text{MarketCap}$, $ER = \ln\text{ExchangeRate}$, $TO = \ln\text{TradeOpenness}$, $IR = \text{Inflation Rate}$ and $GDP = \text{Gross Domestic Product growth rate}$

To operationalise this relationship econometrically, equation (1) morphs into the following linear regression model:

$$MC_t = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 ER_t + \alpha_2 TO_t + \alpha_3 IR_t + \alpha_4 GDP_t + \mu_t \dots \dots \dots (2)$$

Where; α_0 =intercept, $\alpha_1 - \alpha_4$ = long-run parameters and μ_t = stochastic error term

The study applied the “Autoregressive Distributed Lag” (ARDL) approach for short- and long-run predictions because of the nature of time-series data. Even with small sample sizes, the ARDL model works effectively for factors fusing various orders, such as I(0) and I(1) (Paul, 2014). Steps for executing the ARDL bounds-testing framework include checking stationarity, selecting an appropriate lag length (via AIC), testing for cointegration, estimating short- and long-run models, and conducting diagnostic and stability tests. The model’s dynamic ARDL error correcting representation is described as:

$$\Delta MC_t = \alpha_0 + \sum_{i=1}^p \phi_i \Delta MC_{t-1} + \sum_{i=0}^{q1} \beta_i \Delta ER_{t-1} + \sum_{i=0}^{q2} \gamma_i \Delta TO_{t-1} + \sum_{i=0}^{q3} \delta_i \Delta IR_{t-1} + \sum_{i=0}^{q4} \lambda_i \Delta GDP_{t-1} + \theta_1 MC_{t-1} + \theta_2 ER_{t-1} + \theta_3 TO_{t-1} + \theta_4 IR_{t-1} + \theta_5 GDP_{t-1} + \mu_t \dots\dots\dots (3)$$

Δ denotes first difference, lag order length is denoted by p, q1, q2, q3 and q4, and the error term is denoted by μ_t .

$$H_0: \theta_1 = \theta_2 = \theta_3 = \theta_4 = \theta_5 = 0$$

$$H_1: \theta_1 \neq \theta_2 \neq \theta_3 \neq \theta_4 \neq \theta_5 \neq 0$$

Where;

H_0 is the null hypothesis (no long-run relationships)

H_1 is the alternative hypothesis (a long-run relationship exists)

The results of testing the null hypothesis indicate that the F-statistic in the ARDL bound test exceeds the critical value, thus signalling a long-term association among the variables and explaining how explanatory variables affect the dependent variable. The following equation has been used with the model in the long-run:

$$MC_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 ER_t + \beta_2 TO_t + \beta_3 IR_t + \beta_4 GDP_t + \mu_t \dots\dots\dots (4)$$

Where $\beta_1 - \beta_4$ represent the long-run elasticities and μ_t represents the long-run equilibrium error term

The error correction model (ECM) represents the study’s short-term dynamics thusly:

$$\Delta MC_t = \alpha_0 + \sum_{i=1}^p \phi_i \Delta MC_{t-1} + \sum_{i=0}^{q1} \beta_i \Delta ER_{t-1} + \sum_{i=0}^{q2} \gamma_i \Delta TO_{t-1} + \sum_{i=0}^{q3} \delta_i \Delta IR_{t-1} + \sum_{i=0}^{q4} \lambda_i \Delta GDP_{t-1} + \rho ECM_{t-1} + \mu_t \dots\dots\dots (5)$$

Where ϕ_i , β_i , γ_i , δ_i , and λ_i denote the short-run coefficients of the lagged changes in stock market performance, exchange rate, trade openness, inflation rate, and GDP, respectively, capture the short-term dynamic adjustments among the variables in the model.

Also, the coefficient (ρ) represents the rate at which an error correction model (ECM) adapts to long-run equilibrium after a short-term shock. A significant and negative ρ

confirms cointegration and shows the rate at which short-run deviations return to long-run equilibrium.

Finally, we specify ECM as follows:

Equation 6 describes the ECM's rate of recovery from deviation.

$$ECM_{t-1} = MC_{t-1} - (\beta_0 + \beta_1 ER_{t-1} + \beta_2 TO_{t-1} + \beta_3 IR_{t-1} + \beta_4 GDP_{t-1} \dots \dots \dots) \quad (6)$$

Thus, the ECM captures the disequilibrium extent in the previous period and measures how quickly the system converges back to the long-run equilibrium path.

Using this modelling approach, we can accurately assess the short- and long-run causal associations and dynamic adjustments among trade openness, exchange rates, and the performance of Tanzania's stock market.

Unit root test

The study applied the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) and Phillips-Perron (PP) unit root tests to assess the stationarity of the variables under study, as Table 2 further illustrates. As the results illustrate, MarketCap, TradeOpenness, and GDP growth rate were stationary at a level with a constant and a trend, as the significance test statistics (p-values < .05) further confirm. Implicitly, they are integrated of order zero, I(0). Although they become stable after first differencing, InExchangeRate and InflationRate are nonstationary at the level (p-values > .05) and exhibit very significant ADF and PP test statistics (p < .01), suggesting they are integrated of order one, I(1). As Figures 2 and 3 demonstrated, the study further validated a blend of I(0) and I(1) parameters, supporting the ARDL model application for this specific investigation, which can handle such mixes and enable accurate assessment of short- and long-run correlations among the attributes.

Table 2. Augmented Dickey–Fuller and Phillips–Perron Unit Root Test Results

Unit Root Test	Augmented Dickey–Fuller		Phillips–Perron		Order of integration
	Level constant and trend	First difference Constant trend	Level constant and trend	First difference Constant trend	
InMarketCap	-3.137 (0.0239)		-2.877 (0.0481)		I(0)
InExchangeRate	-1.149 (0.6950)	-6.879 (0.00)	-1.128 (0.7037)	-6.909 (0.00)	I(1)
InTradeOpenness	-4.355 (0.0004)		-4.359 (0.0004)		I(0)
InflationRate	-1.642 (0.4610)	-9.430 (0.00)	-1.576 (0.4959)	-9.457 (0.00)	I(1)
GDP growth rate	-7.200 (0.0000)		-7.279 (0.0000)		I(0)

Figure 2. Trends of lnMarketCap, lnExchangeRate, lnTradeOpenness, InflationRate and GDP growth rate

Figure 3. Trends of lnExchangeRate and InflationRate after first difference

Descriptive Statistics

The descriptive statistics of the variables are based on 72 observations, as shown in Table 3. The natural logarithm of market capitalisation (lnMarketCap), on average, equals 9.192, with the value's dispersion, as measured by the standard deviation, equalling 1.092. This outcome shows some variability in Tanzania's stock market performance across the period under review. Exchange rate variations are minimal, as the reduced standard deviation of 0.251 and the mean of 7.484 indicate. The average and standard deviation of the respective trade openness (lnTradeOpenness) are 6.323 and 0.495,

respectively. These modest peripheral values indicate Tanzania’s increased exposure to global trade. The 15.48% mean and 1.668 standard deviation signal that the nation had substantial inflation. This represents times of price volatility linked to sensitive investor sentiment and macroeconomic volatility. A 2.077 GDP growth standard deviation, coupled with a 6.119% mean, among other indicators, illustrates that growth remains non-uniform despite the expanding economy, due to a limited number of listed firms and informal businesses, thereby limiting the translation of economic growth into market outcomes (Oladejo et al., 2025).

Table 3. Descriptive statistics

Variable	Obs.	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min.	Max.
lnMarketCap	72	9.192	1.092	3.089	10.074
lnExchangeRate	72	7.484	0.251	7.055	7.748
lnTradeOpenness	72	6.323	0.495	4.894	7.433
InflationRate	72	15.48	1.668	12.87	19.086
GDP growth rate	72	6.119	2.077	2.585	12.444

Correlation and multicollinearity test

The pairwise correlation matrix and VIF in Table 4 capture the associations among the selected variables and assess multicollinearity. Further analysis shows that lnMarketCap has a positive and highly significant correlation with lnExchangeRate (0.711) and lnTradeOpenness (0.434), thus suggesting that a decline in the exchange rate and a rise in trade openness can improve Tanzania’s stock market. lnExchangeRate demonstrates a significant positive relationship with lnTradeOpenness (0.450) and InflationRate (0.621), thus confirming that currency movements are adjustable with trade and inflation. InflationRate has a weak association with lnMarketCap (0.233), whereas GDP growth rate has a weak and statistically insignificant connection with lnMarketCap (0.028), yet is strongly and negatively correlated with lnTradeOpenness (-0.743). In other words, trade openness is associated with declining GDP growth. The 2.44 VIF mean and below a threshold of 10 confirms non-significant multicollinearity. These correlations further underscore the importance of inflation, trade openness, and exchange rates for stock market activity and performance, while signalling a limited impact of GDP growth.

Table 4. Pairwise correlations matrix and Variance Inflation Factor

Variables	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)
(1) lnMarketCap	1.000				
(2) lnExchangeRate	0.711***	1.000			
(3) lnTradeOpenness	0.434***	0.450***	1.000		
(4) Inflation Rate	0.233**	0.621***	0.185	1.000	
(5) GDP growth rate	0.028	-0.088	-0.743***	-0.050	1.000
VIF		2.44	3.5	1.71	2.77
1/VIF		0.409	0.285	0.586	0.362
Mean VIF					2.6

*** $p < 0.001$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.1$

Zivot-Andrews structural break unit root test

The study employed the Zivot-Andrews structural break unit root test to determine potential single endogenous structural breaks in the time-series data. It applied the Model C (break in intercept and trend) deemed suitable for macroeconomic time series likely to experience structural changes because of policy reforms or economic shocks. Table 5 results signal that *lnMarketCap*, *lnTradeOpenness*, and *GDP* invalidate the null hypothesis of a unit root at a 5% significance level because of their more negative test statistics than the corresponding critical values. Moreover, the estimated break dates in 2014Q4, 2019Q3, and 2018Q2, respectively, in Figure 4 could correspond to structural adjustment periods in Tanzania’s economic and financial environment, including capital market reforms and trade policy developments.

Also, *lnExchangeRate* and *InflationRate* do not substantiate the null hypothesis of a unit root, primarily because their test statistics are higher than the critical values. Implicitly, these variables persist as non-stationary even after structural breaks have been accounted for, implying that seemingly intractable macroeconomic shocks can still influence exchange-rate and inflation dynamics. These Zivot-Andrews results affirm how the variables are integrated of mixed orders, which buttress the ARDL modelling framework’s suitability, which allows the estimation of long-run relationships among variables integrated at varying orders while accounting for data structural changes.

Table 5: Zivot-Andrews Structural Break Unit Root Test

Variables	T-Statistics	1%	5%	10%	Year of Break	Result
<i>lnMarketCap</i>	-4.720	-4.93	-4.42	-4.11	2014q4	Stationary
<i>lnExchangeRate</i>	-3.373	-4.93	-4.42	-4.11	2017q3	Non-stationary
<i>lnTradeOpenness</i>	-4.176	-4.93	-4.42	-4.11	2019q3	Stationary
<i>InflationRate</i>	-3.229	-4.93	-4.42	-4.11	2008q4	Non-stationary
<i>GDP growth rate</i>	-7.795	-4.93	-4.42	-4.11	2018q2	Stationary

Figure 4. Zivot-Andrews Structural Break Unit Root Test graph

Bounds test for cointegration analysis.

The ARDL bounds testing procedure enabled the study to determine whether a long-run equilibrium connection exists among market capitalisation, exchange rate, trade openness, inflation rate, and GDP. This test compared the calculated F-statistic with M. Hashem Pesaran, Yongcheol Shin, and Richard Smith's (2001) proposed lower- and upper-bound critical values. In this regard, Table 6 indicates having conducted the bounds test under Case III (unrestricted intercept and no trend) with $k = 4$ explanatory variables. As the data further illustrate, the estimated F-statistic (5.479) exceeds the upper-bound critical value (4.591) at the 5% significance level, as informed by Sebastian Kripfganz and Daniel Schneider's (2020) finite-sample critical values. The associated p-values (0.006 and 0.039), below conventional significance levels, further support the rejection of the null hypothesis of no level relationship.

Considering the bounds testing decision rule stating that if the computed F-statistic outstrips the upper-bound critical value, then the null hypothesis of no cointegration ought to be rejected. Such an outcome suggests a long-run relationship among the variables. In other words, there is a long-run cointegration for market capitalisation, exchange rate, trade openness, inflation rate, and GDP. This outcome also validates the application of the ARDL error correction framework in estimating both short-run dynamics and long-run equilibrium effects among variables.

Table 6. Bounds Test for Cointegration Analysis

Critical Value	Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1%	4.088	4.591
5%	3.005	4.275
10%	2.525	3.681
P-Value	0.006	0.039
F-Statistics		5.479

Homoskedasticity, no autocorrelation, and normality of the test

The study further conducted several post-estimation diagnostic tests to determine satisfaction of classical regression assumptions, principally to validate the ARDL estimation. To accomplish this task, the study deployed White's test to detect heteroskedasticity in residuals and determine the constancy of the error term variance across observations. Then, the study applied the Breusch–Godfrey Serial Correlation LM test to evaluate the presence of autocorrelation in the estimated model residuals. Subsequently, the Shapiro-Wilk test enabled the study to assess the residual normality. Together, these diagnostic procedures ensured that the study's ARDL model satisfied key homoskedasticity assumptions, the absence of serial correlation, and error terms normality, and thus, augmented the reliability of the estimated coefficients and subsequent inference.

Results and Discussion

Lag-order selection criteria

Initially, the study determined the optimal lag length using standard lag-order selection criteria ahead of estimating the ARDL model. The study considered several information criteria, particularly the Akaike Information Criterion (AIC), Final Prediction Error (FPE), Hannan–Quinn Information Criterion (HQIC), and Schwarz Bayesian Information Criterion (SBIC) during the selection process. These are atypical time-series econometrics criteria for determining the lag structure best balancing the model-fit and parsimony.

In Table 7, the lag-order selection results indicate that lag 1 yields the lowest values of AIC (-0.035582), FPE (6.7e-07), HQIC (0.352405), and SBIC (0.943613) relative to alternative lag orders. The minimum AIC value occurs at lag 1 made this study adopt lag 1 as optimal lag length. Eventually, the study estimated ARDL model using ARDL(1,1,1,1,1) specifications to establish both short-run dynamics and long-run correlations among market capitalisation, exchange rate, trade openness, inflation rate, and GDP in Tanzania.

Table 7. Lag Length Selection

Lag	LL	LR	df	p	FPE	AIC	HQIC	SBIC
0	-273.27				0.00247	8.18436	8.24902	8.34756
1	31.2098	608.96	25	0	6.7e-07*	-.035582*	.352405*	.943613*
2	49.7203	37.021	25	0.057	8.20E-07	0.155286	0.8666	1.95048
3	69.1641	38.888	25	0.038	9.90E-07	0.318702	1.35333	2.92989
4	101.752	65.176*	25	0	8.40E-07	0.095527	1.45348	3.52271

Diagnostic test results

Table 8's diagnostic test results affirm the ARDL regression model's assumptions and reinforce its statistical reliability and robustness. Significantly, the results are devoid of any heteroscedasticity evidence in residuals, based on White's test statistic ($\chi^2(54) = 70.11$, p-value = 0.0693, which is above the 0.05 cutoff. Also, the Breusch-Godfrey serial correlation LM test (p = 0.1877) indicates that the error terms are independently distributed over time. Implicitly, there is no evidence of autocorrelation. Furthermore, the Shapiro–Wilk test (p = 0.0586) reveals normally distributed residuals. These diagnostics collectively affirm that the analysis model fulfils the traditional ARDL homoscedasticity regression requirements, with no autocorrelation coupled with normality. These results further confirm the accuracy of the estimated coefficients and the model-based conclusions' dependability.

Table 8. Diagnostic Test Results

	Null Hypothesis	Test Statistics	Decision
White's test ($\chi^2(54)$)	Homoskedasticity	70.11 (0.0693)	Do not reject H0
The Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation LM Test	No autocorrelation	1.736 (0.1877)	Do not reject H0
Shapiro–Wilk	Normality of the error term	5.67 (0.0586)	Do not reject H0

ARDL Regression Results

The short-run and long-run estimates from the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) model Table 9 depict the relationship between exchange rate, trade openness, inflation, GDP, on the one hand, and stock market performance in Tanzania, on the other. The exchange rate ($\ln\text{ExchangeRate}$) in the long-run has a positive and statistically significant bearing on market capitalisation (coefficient = 2.555, $p = 0.005$). In other words, exchange rate movements significantly influence stock market performance. Meanwhile, an exchange rate spike in Tanzania usually inflects currency depreciation, which can boost competitiveness among export-oriented firms and heighten foreign investor participation. In consequence, domestic assets and shares become relatively cheaper and, thus, raise stock market capitalisation. Hypothesis H_1 is thus credible, making the study results also align with El-Diftar (2023) with similar findings in emerging economies, and Abille and Meçik's (2023) findings on exchange rate dynamics significantly affecting stock market performance in selected Sub-Saharan African countries.

Furthermore, the results indicate respective coefficients of 1.192 ($p = 0.033$) and 0.322 ($p = 0.018$) to signal positive and statistically significant long-run relationships between trade openness ($\ln\text{TradeOpenness}$) and GDP, and stock market performance. Such evidence validates hypotheses H_2 and H_4 . In other words, heightened integration into international trade and overall economic expansion fosters stock market development. Moreover, greater trade openness engenders capital flows, enhances market liquidity, and boosts corporate growth opportunities to strengthen subsequently stock market performance. Indubitably, trade openness expands markets and exposes the domestic economy to external shocks and global market volatility (Missango & Mwankwemwa, 2025). As such, its net effect relies on macroeconomic stability and institutional capacity.

On the other hand, inflation lacks a statistically significant long-run bearing on stock market performance ($p = 0.22$). Indeed, tenacious inflationary pressures have already been integrated into long-term investor expectations and asset pricing decisions. Similarly, Keswani et al. (2024) and Peter et al. (2024) reported limited long-run inflation effect on stock market returns in India and Nigeria, respectively.

Evidentially, exchange rate changes in the short-run persist as positively significant (coefficient = 0.681, $p = 0.047$), with short-term currency movements instantly afflicting stock market performance. Also, a negative short-run inflation effect (coefficient = -0.124 , $p = 0.068$) suggests that soaring inflation gradually erodes investor confidence and enervates market performance in short-term price adjustments. Kilian and Zhou

(2022) and Bernanke and Blanchard (2025) in the US market and Mfugale and Olomi (2023) in Tanzania produced similar results. Nevertheless, the short-run trade openness and GDP impacts are statistically insignificant, as their bearing on the stock market is primarily realisable over the long-term.

Also, the negative and highly significant (ECT = -0.498 , $p = 0.000$) error correction term (ECT) confirm a long-run equilibrium relationship among variables. About 49.8% of short-run disequilibrium is corrected each quarter, which demonstrates a relatively fast long-run equilibrium adjustment. Meanwhile, the constant term ($_cons = -8.533$, $p = 0.009$) manifests the drift component of the differenced model while capturing the average baseline adjustment in market capitalisation with constant explanatory variables. The ARDL results further signal how exchange rate stability, economic growth, and trade integration explain long-term Tanzania's stock market performance. Inflation mainly afflicts the market in the short-run. These results concur with systems theory's treatment of the exchange rate, inflation rate, GDP, and stock market as interconnected financial and economic system components since changes in one variable spell a shift for other elements, both internally and externally.

Table 9. Short-run and Long-run Results

Long-term Results: Dependent variable lnMarketCap				
Variables	Coefficient	Std. err.	t	P>t
lnExchangeRate L1.	2.555	0.885	2.89	0.005**
lnTradeOpenness L1.	1.192	0.548	2.18	0.033**
InflationRate L1.	-0.143	0.115	-1.24	0.22
GDP growth rate L1.	0.322	0.132	2.44	0.018**
Short Run Results: Dependent variable lnMarketCap				
lnExchangeRate D1.	0.681	0.336	2.03	0.047***
lnTradeOpenness D1.	0.303	0.459	0.66	0.511
InflationRate D1.	-0.124	0.067	-1.86	0.068*
GDP growth rate D1.	0.06	0.085	0.7	0.485
$_cons$	-8.533	3.169	-2.69	0.009**
ECT (-1)	-0.498	0.107	-4.64	0.000***
R-squared	0.7549			
F-statistic	20.88			0.000***
Adj R-squared	0.7187			
Root MSE	0.5577			

*Note: Significance levels: *** $p < 0.001$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.1$*

Robustness Check

Cumulative Sum and Cumulative Sum of Squares diagnostic tests

Figures 5 and 6 present, respectively, the Cumulative Sum (CUSUM) and Cumulative Sum of Squares (CUSUMSQ) diagnostic tests that the study applied, coupled with the ARDL model, to evaluate stock market performance. Both CUSUM and CUSUMSQ are vital tools in evaluating model parameters' consistency over time. Specifically, CUSUM

is sensitive to gradual changes, whereas CUSUMSQ is effective in determining sudden structural changes. The results indicate that the CUSUM plot remained within the 5% significance boundary, implying no upward instability, which also confirms stability among model parameters throughout the sampling period. Notably, when the test statistics are at the top critical boundary, the CUSUMSQ plot indicates a structural break between 2008Q1 and 2010Q2. In other words, the global financial crisis significantly affected Tanzania and other emerging economies during this review period. These macroeconomic shocks temporarily frustrated the long-run equilibrium relationships among exchange rates, trade openness, and market capitalisation. In fact, the overall model remained within critical bounds regardless of short-term instability, which signals general long-run stability, even during the structural disturbance period, when financial instability and uncertainty in global markets likely induced the exchange rate dynamics, trade flows, and investor behaviour in the domestic stock market.

Figure 5. Cumulative Sum (CUSUM)

Figure 6. Cumulative Sum of the Squares (CUSUM sq)

Granger Causality Test

The study also carried out a Granger causality Wald test to determine the direction of the effects among research variables. The additional evidence stemming from the results further supports the ARDL findings. Table 10 results indicate respective chi-square statistics of 6.214 ($p = 0.013$) and 6.150 ($p = 0.013$) for the exchange rate and GDP Granger-causing stock market performance. Changes in these macroeconomic variables precede and facilitate the prediction of movements in market capitalisation. This outcome concurs with the ARDL long-run estimates of both variables being significant determinants of stock market performance.

Moreover, trade openness Granger-causes stock market performance at the 10% significance level ($\chi^2 = 3.605$, $p = 0.058$). This result additionally backs the positive long-run effect of trade openness in the ARDL model. On the other hand, as inflation does not Granger-cause stock market performance, changes in inflation may not systematically and necessarily predict stock market movements. This outcome conforms to the ARDL results, indicating inflation as statistically insignificant in the long-run and only marginally significant in the short-run.

Furthermore, the study found no reverse causality from stock market performance to exchange rate, trade openness, inflation, or GDP. Implicitly, a unidirectional causal relationship exists, with macroeconomic conditions influencing stock market performance instead of the stock market impacting macroeconomic fundamentals. Suggestively, Tanzania's stock market remains relatively smaller than the broader economy; its movements, therefore, are unlikely to catalyse macroeconomic indicators such as GDP or exchange rates. This causality analysis confirms that exchange rate movements, GDP, and trade openness are key drivers of stock market performance in Tanzania, thus further emboldening the robustness of the ARDL findings.

Table 10. Granger Causality Wald Test

Null Hypothesis	chi2	Prob>Chi2
lnExchangeRate does not Granger-cause lnMarketCap	6.2143	0.013**
lnTradeOpenness does not Granger-cause lnMarketCap	3.6048	0.058*
InflationRate does not Granger-cause lnMarketCap	1.2276	0.268
GDP growth does not Granger-cause lnMarketCap	6.1502	0.013**
lnMarketCap does not Granger-cause lnExchangeRate	0.478	0.489
lnMarketCap does not Granger-cause lnTradeOpenness	0.742	0.389
lnMarketCap does not Granger-cause InflationRate	1.328	0.249
lnMarketCap does not Granger-cause GDP growth	2.018	0.155

*Note: Significance levels: *** $p < 0.001$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.1$*

Conclusion

Overall, this assessment of the statistical relationships among exchange rates, trade openness, GDP growth rate, and the performance of Tanzania's stock market indicate a

significant and positive long-run linkage among exchange rates, trade openness, GDP, and stock market capitalisation, but with no significant relationship with inflation. The focus of the inquiry was the Dar es Salaam Stock Exchange, using time-series data drawn from 2006Q1 to 2023Q4. Whereas short-run trade openness and GDP emerged to be statistically insignificant, meaning their bearing on stock market capitalisation materialises over time, the exchange rate remained positively significant, signalling how short-term currency movements affect stock market capitalisation. Moreover, inflation's minimal but significant negative influence in the short-run reflects an immediate monetary policy response, price adjustments, and a change in investor attitudes. The findings are consistent with the systems theory, which presumes the interconnection between macroeconomic variables and the stock market within a broader financial and economic system. As such, stock market performance cannot be assessed in isolation, as it responds to the overall economy. Hence, enhancing stock market capitalisation in developing economies such as Tanzania requires improved monetary and fiscal policies to enhance investor confidence, promote stock market performance, and purposively strengthen macroeconomic stability.

Implications

The study results offer theoretical insights into the need to consider the stated relationship when evaluating stock market performance. Significantly, these results extend the application of systems theory, which treats exchange rates, inflation, GDP growth rate, trade openness, and the stock market as components of the financial and economic system that interact with one another. Moreover, the study findings could serve as a basis for the Tanzania government to further boost fiscal and monetary policies and regulations to raise investor confidence and foster listing activity to improve stock market capitalisation. Such an intervention can accelerate the 2050 development vision implementation, as the stock market is an invaluable source of development projects' financing.

Limitations and Areas for Future Studies

The study limitations include its uses of data from 2006Q1 to 2023Q4 generated from a single country, which may not necessarily reflect global stock market trends. Thus, future studies could broaden the data base using multiple countries and incorporate external factors left out in the current study, which otherwise could affect the results. Also, the study's dependence on quantitative time-series data limits the grasping of stakeholders' perceptions. To address this limitation, future research would employ mixed methods for the qualitative dimension to complement the quantitative to yield more robust, comprehensive insights into stock market dynamics. Subsequently, the limited duration of 72 quarters for the sample could introduce attrition bias and, thus, undermine its representativeness. Considering this shortcoming, further research could accommodate more observations for enhanced results.

Author Contributions

All authors contributed to the study conception and design. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

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Data Availability Statement

The data supporting the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

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Not applicable.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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